

IMPROVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR SHAPING THE SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF A1 LEVEL STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article examines the improvement of technologies for the formation of sociolinguistic competence of students at level A1 in English lessons.

Keywords: sociolinguistic competence, level A1, English language, teaching, methodology.

Culturally oriented approaches to teaching foreign languages force methodologists to create new technologies, study in detail the components of foreign language communicative competence and, as a result, develop exercises for their formation. Students' mastery of the proposed learning content involves completing a cycle of lessons on the formation of sociolinguistic competence.

In this article we propose the technology of formation of sociolinguistic competence of students of the level developed by us. They are related to the stages of work on speech material proposed by modern foreign methodologists within the framework of the communicative methodology of teaching a foreign language: the stage of formation of sociolinguistic knowledge, the stage of improvement of sociolinguistic skills and the stage of development of sociolinguistic abilities [2]. For this purpose, we have developed a private system of exercises for mastering speaking in dialogical speech, which is of particular interest in the conditions of introduction of the oral part of students of the A1 level in foreign languages. The private system includes exercises of three types: exercises for analysis of the communicative situation, recognition, definition and justification of the used registers of communication; conditional speech exercises; speech exercises. The purpose of the first stage is the formation of sociolinguistic knowledge of communication in English within the framework provided by the training program; formation of the need to study a foreign language and knowledge of a foreign culture. In subsequent lessons, students at level A1 perform exercises on analyzing a communicative situation, recognizing, defining and justifying the used registers of communication; conditional speech imitation and substitution exercises on the functional acquisition of a set of two adjacent lines in a dialogue, connected structurally and situationally, that is, dialogic unity or microdialogue sequentially in three tones of communication. At this stage, the attention of students at level A1 is

focused mainly on the form of new lexical units. Further, we use speech training situations in the formation of speech skills, since the language form memorized outside the situation is not marked by the type of relations between the interlocutors and cannot be used in the future in real communication situations. A large informative list of elements for substitution ensures regular repetition of the sample in the same type of conditions. It should be noted that the analysis of modern domestic and foreign textbooks on the English language made it possible to identify pragmatic clichés (speech clichés, formulas of speech etiquette) used in the English national-linguocultural community in the official, neutral and unofficial registers in various communicative functions of communication (expressing surprise, approving, etc.). When compiling the exercises of this stage, we are guided by the principles of communicative focus, dialogue of cultures, functionality, stylistic differentiation, problematic, which are used within the framework of the information-receptive, reproductive, heuristic methods and the method of problematic presentation. All assignments for the exercises and the situations themselves are offered to students of level A1 in English and in brackets in their native language.

The stage of formation of sociolinguistic knowledge involves both individual work of students of level A1 on the perception and comprehension of the material on the essence and meaning of sociolinguistic competence, analysis of the sociolinguistic conditions of the communicative situation; and pair work, during which students solve a variety of cognitive and communicative problems. The teacher organizes the training, acts as a speech partner, and, if necessary, explores new speech patterns of English behavior in communication situations together with the students [3]. As training tools at the first stage, we propose using exercises to analyze the communicative situation, exercises to determine the registers of communication, conditional speech exercises based on substantive supports in the form of substitution tables.

The goal of the second stage is to improve sociolinguistic communication skills in English and improve the need to study a foreign language and knowledge of a foreign culture. Here we are guided by the principles of communicative focus, dialogue of cultures, functionality, stylistic differentiation, problematic, speech behavioral strategies and autonomy of students, which we used within the framework of the information-receptive, reproductive, heuristic methods and the method of problematic presentation. Students at level A1, having defined the communication register for each of the situations, use functional models of dialogue and communicate at the level of controlled

extended dialogue. The volume of linguistic material in the formation of sociolinguistic competence in comparison with traditional teaching is tripled due to speech clichés in the official, neutral, and unofficial registers. For a more solid consolidation of speech material, in particular, for the formation of flexibility, stability, and automation of the skill [1], we suggest that students at the stage of improving skills also go the way "from above" [3], i.e. from a sample dialogue to free dialogic speech. To do this, the teacher first needs to organize the perception of the sample dialogue with graphic support and subsequent verification of reading comprehension in order to generally understand its meaning, identify the characters and their positions. Further work on the sample dialogue is analytical in nature, which implies, in addition to identifying and "appropriating" the features of this dialogue in the form of speech clichés, elliptical sentences, addresses, emotional remarks, an analysis of the sociolinguistic conditions of the communicative situation, as well as determining the social statuses and roles of the communicants, their relationships, place and register of communication.

After this, it is advisable for students of level A1 to offer a dramatization of the dialogue by roles in order to fully "appropriate" this dialogue. The next stage of working with the sample dialogue is working with a substitution table. The knowledge of conversational clichés and formulas of speech etiquette, previously formed in dialogic unities and an expanded dialogue based on the functional model of dialogue, as well as the skills of using them in the official, neutral and unofficial registers are now used by students of level A1 in conditions of changing the addressee and sender of messages, the place of communication and the relationships between the speakers. One of the most important skills in the proposed technology is the skill of recognizing communication registers and the skill of recognizing speech communication formulas. To form and improve them in the learning process, we propose recognizing the communication registers of the participants in communicative acts. The criterion for completing/not completing the task is the fact of recognizing/not recognizing the belonging of a particular cliché or formula of speech etiquette to a certain communication register. This task is intended for oral completion, analysis and group or pair discussion. The following exercises are analogous to the previous ones, but with deliberately admitted errors in the use of registers. Students are asked to determine the register in which the interlocutors communicate; to prove that the use of one of the registers is

wrong; to choose the correct tonality of communication in order to avoid a communication failure.

All tasks for the formation of speech skills and the development of speech ability correspond to stable and variable requirements for exercises [2]. Individual and group work at the second stage is carried out during the execution of exercises on the analysis of the communicative situation, recognition, definition and justification of the used registers of communication (students independently and/or jointly analyze and discuss the sociolinguistic context of the communicative situation). Pair work is implemented during the solution of numerous communicative and cognitive tasks. As teaching tools at the second stage, we also used content and semantic supports, substitution tables, speech exercises in dramatizing dialogues with functional models of dialogues, but the teacher uses English and his native language in the lesson. The goal of the final stage of the formation of the sociolinguistic competence is the development and creative application of sociolinguistic and speech skills and the development of the need to study a foreign language and knowledge of a foreign culture. As in the previous two stages, the teacher organizes the learning process, acts as a competent speech partner and, if necessary, explores with the student's new speech models of behavior of the English in communication situations, translating incomprehensible moments into their native language. The main objective of the series of exercises in the study of specific situations is to teach students of level A1 to apply and justify sociolinguistic knowledge, to promote the development of sociolinguistic skills and to make correct strategic and operational decisions.

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